

Immersion in Isolation: Gaming Experience, Cognitive Filtering, and Disconnection during COVID-19

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“[...] To alleviate the boredom, after catching a fish, Kingfisher would press all three buttons before swallowing the fish. Pressing the buttons has gradually become somewhat of a new technological ritual.”

—In “Innovation,” *Wild Wise Weird* (2024)

Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has profoundly disrupted social routines, prompting widespread self-isolation and the adoption of digital coping strategies. This study examined the relationship between duration of self-isolation/social distancing, gameplay experiences in *Animal Crossing: New Horizons* (ACNH), and players' perceived disconnection from the real world. Grounded in Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITTT) and employing Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) analytics, we analyze data from 640 players across 29 countries. Results reveal a nonlinear inverse U-shaped relationship between self-isolation/social distancing duration and real-world disconnection: disconnection increases during initial isolation but declines beyond approximately two weeks, suggesting cognitive adaptation. Moreover, the association between game-playing frequency and real-world disconnection is conditional on the level of immersiveness—proxied by the perceived richness of game experience. Specifically, among players with high immersiveness, increased game-playing frequency predicts greater disconnection. Conversely, for players with low immersiveness, higher game-playing frequency is associated with reduced disconnection. Meanwhile, aesthetic appeal and imaginativeness exhibit ambiguous moderating effects. Findings indicate that emotional resonance and informational depth, rather than screen time alone, critically shape gaming's psychological outcomes. The study advances integration between cognitive filtering and value-absorption mechanisms and highlights the importance of designing digital environments that balance immersion with psychological safeguards.

Keywords: COVID-19; self-isolation; social distancing; gaming experiences; rich experience, real-world disconnection.

1. Introduction

The outbreak of COVID-19 has raised various mental health and psychological issues globally, such as anxiety, fear, depression, stress disorder (including PTSD), panic, feeling insecure, hypervigilance, intolerance, discrimination toward particular races (Asian), stigmatization (toward Chinese), close-minded attitude, hopelessness, despair, grief, bereavement, a profound loss of purpose in life, feeling uncertain and loss of control (Usher, Durkin, & Bhullar, 2020). This pandemic situation has led to widespread (1) social distancing, (2) self-quarantine, and (3) self-isolation, leading to mass quarantine with impacts on well-being, especially mental health and psychological challenges (Suppawittaya, Yiemphat, & Yasri, 2020). These three social alteration methods disrupt daily routines and significantly reduce in-person social interaction.

During a homebound period, many individuals turned to self-entertainment digitally, with *Animal Crossing: New Horizons* (ACNH) quickly becoming one of the most widely played games during the pandemic, as it was launched at a very strategic time (Comerford, 2020). Released in March 2020, just as global lockdowns began (Onyeaka, Anumudu, Al-Sharify, Egele-Godswill, & Mbaegbu, 2021), ACNH provided a relaxing and

customizable virtual space that offered psychological relief and social connection for millions of players worldwide (Pearce et al., 2022). Basically, ACNH is a life simulation game played in real-time (Zhu, 2021). It is a multiplayer online game providing players with rich social interaction (Tong et al., 2021), with an expansive and varied player base (Parkatti, 2021). ACNH's game mechanics are shared mechanics. Thus, fostering social interaction among players in the virtual world.

Empirical research indicates that ACNH served as a coping mechanism during the pandemic by meeting fundamental psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness, in line with self-determination theory (SDT) (Yee & Sng, 2022). Its social functions, such as visiting other players' islands, were associated with reduced loneliness (Lewis, Trojovsky, & Jameson, 2021), although more frequent gameplay sometimes correlated with higher anxiety, especially social anxiety (Wang, Sheng, & Wang, 2019). Qualitative findings further revealed that ACNH allowed players to recreate important social rituals, including weddings and graduations, within a virtual environment (Tong et al., 2021). These practices provided stability, social connection, and meaningful routines at a time of global uncertainty or crisis (Comerford, 2020).

While such findings emphasize the potential benefits of ACNH for psychological and social well-being during the pandemic, they also highlight the complexity of gaming experiences. Prior scholarship suggests that video games can mitigate loneliness and facilitate social bonding (Carras et al., 2018; Kowert & Kaye, 2018), yet excessive engagement may also foster disengagement from offline contexts to the point of game addiction (Yang & Gong, 2021), particularly when real-world social opportunities are already constrained (Chang, Chen, & Hsieh, 2022). Thus, the effects of gaming are shaped not only by frequency of play but also by the quality of the experience (Schmidt, Zadtootaghaj, Wang, & Möller, 2021), including subjective perceptions of media richness (Liao, Huang, Cheng, & Teng, 2020), aesthetic and entertaining appeal (Possler & Klimmt, 2023), and creativity (Voiskounsky, Yermolova, Yagolkovskiy, & Khromova, 2017).

From the standpoint of flow theory (Csikszentmihalyi, Montijo, & Mouton, 2018), games with strong experiential and aesthetic qualities can promote deep immersion (Yli-Olli, 2024), allowing players to feel a concentrated focus and enjoyment in in-game activities (Bodzin, Junior, Hammond, & Anastasio, 2021). Media richness theory from Daft & Lengel (1986) similarly suggests that richer and more vivid environments enhance emotional expression and engagement (Syed & Shaheen, 2025). Additionally, literature on aesthetic experience argues that visually and imaginatively engaging content intensifies affective responses, such as empathy and other emotional responses (Brinck, 2018), enhances personal meaning, and increases the perceived value of the activity (Pelowski, Markey, Forster, Gerger, & Leder, 2017). In the case of ACNH, these perceptual qualities may heighten the sense of presence within the virtual world (Pallavicini, Pepe, & Minissi, 2019), shaping whether gameplay enhances feelings of connection or contributes to disconnection from everyday life (Isbister, 2016). In this study, the player's feelings toward ACNH are considered as their authentic feelings for the game, or

real feelings, represented by rich experience, aesthetics, and imaginativeness, which are induced by emotional attachments and interpersonal attraction to virtual characters (Coulson, Barnett, Ferguson, & Gould, 2012), or the in-game avatar.

Despite increasing recognition of the importance of perceptual factors, limited research has explored how these dimensions interact with gameplay behavior to influence social outcomes, especially during the social distancing period of the COVID-19 pandemic. Using the behavioral lens of ACNH gaming, this study addresses this gap by investigating: (1) whether time spent in self-isolation/social distancing is linked to players' disconnection from the outside world, (2) whether frequency of play relates to this sense of disconnection, and (3) whether players' feelings about the game, i.e., rich experience, aesthetics, and imaginativeness, moderate the relationship between gameplay frequency and real-world disconnection. By examining these research questions, this study aims to contribute to a more nuanced understanding of how perceptual factors shape gaming experiences, particularly in contexts of restricted social interaction. The specific study aims are as follows:

1. Examining how the time spent in self-isolation is associated with real-world disconnection among ACNH players.
2. Examining how the frequency of playing games is associated with players' disconnection from the outside world.
3. Examining the moderating effect of players' authentic feelings about ACNH, i.e., rich experience, aesthetics, and imaginativeness of the game, on the association between the frequency of playing games and their real-world disconnection.

Findings are expected to contribute to understanding the association between game perceptual factors, such as rich experience, aesthetics, and imaginativeness, and game-playing experiences. Insights gained from this study are expected to extend theoretical and empirical knowledge of the psychological and social functions of video games, particularly ACNH, while also informing the design of digital environments that foster well-being and meaningful connection both in times of crisis and in everyday life.

2. Methods

2.1. Theoretical Foundation

The present study is grounded in Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITT), which explains complex human behavior through micro-level cognitive interactions (Vuong, La, & Nguyen, 2025b). GITT posits that individuals continuously process incoming information through a dynamic interplay of cognitive filters, value systems, and contextual cues, resulting in a granular network of interactions that shape perception, decision-making, and behavior (Vuong, La, & Nguyen, 2025a). In the context of ACNH gameplay during the COVID-19 pandemic, GITT provides a robust theoretical scaffold for understanding how players' emotional experiences and cognitive engagement with

the game interact with broader psychosocial conditions, such as self-isolation and detachment from the outside world.

From the GITT perspective, real-world disconnection emerges as an outcome of information processing in which reduced interaction with external reality coincides with the mind's informational system being predominantly occupied by ACNH-related inputs. This outcome results from the interactions among three primary types of information: (1) in-game information, (2) information within the player's mind, and (3) information derived from the surrounding environment. One of GITT's core principles is granularity, which asserts that informational and energetic capacity within any system—including the human mind—is finite. Consequently, the mind can only absorb and process a limited amount of incoming information at any given time. As internal informational units accumulate, so does entropy, which can be calculated using Shannon (1948)'s formula:

$$H(X) = - \sum_{i=1}^n P(x_i) \log_2 P(x_i)$$

Here, $H(X)$ denotes the informational entropy of the player's mind X , with informational units $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ and corresponding probabilities $\{P(x_1), P(x_2), \dots, P(x_n)\}$. Each probability $P(x_i)$ expresses how likely the information x_i is to occur. Entropy increases rapidly when numerous informational units coexist without prioritization, reaching its maximum when all information carries equal probability, $P(x_i) = \frac{1}{n}$. To reduce the entropy, the mind has two main strategies: (i) organizing, evaluating, and assigning higher probabilities to information deemed valuable; or (ii) reducing informational load by filtering out content perceived as irrelevant or costly to process. Accordingly, real-world disconnection may arise when players' cognition increasingly prioritizes game-derived information, making it less likely that external environmental cues are absorbed and integrated.

During COVID-19, prolonged self-isolation reduced the availability and variability of external information, with such content becoming repetitive and deprioritized. In contrast, the amount and diversity of in-game information increased as players spent more time engaging with ACNH as a form of entertainment and emotional relief. This shift in environmental conditions alters the types of activities available and, consequently, the information the mind interacts with, leading to cognitive recalibration. This adaptive process can be formalized using Bayes' theorem (Gill, 2014; Vuong, Nguyen, Ho, & La, 2025):

$$P(X | I_A) = \frac{P(I_A | X)P(X)}{\sum P(I_A | X_i)P(X_i)}$$

Where $P(X | I_A)$ represents the updated cognitive state after exposure to information from the external environment I_A . If this external information is gradually replaced by in-game information I_B , the mind updates its cognitive priorities toward I_B . Thus, during periods of self-isolation or social distancing, players may recalibrate their value systems

toward virtual engagement and escapism. This recalibration may either intensify disconnection from physical reality or provide compensatory emotional experiences, depending on the duration and intensity of isolation. Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Players who engage in longer or higher-intensity self-isolation/social distancing will report higher levels of real-world disconnection during ACNH gaming.

When assessing how gaming may contribute to real-world disconnection, it is not only gameplay frequency or game mechanics that matter, but also players' emotional engagement. Authentic emotional responses to the gaming experience are particularly influential due to their resonance. Emotions are central to player experience and are integral to how games create unique psychological effects (Bopp, Mekler, & Opwis, 2016). GITT conceptualizes cognition as a dynamic system of micro-interactions where each thought, feeling, or behavior emerges from layered, context-sensitive processing (Vuong & Nguyen, 2025). Games frequently evoke powerful emotions such as enjoyment, excitement, achievement, and belonging, triggered by interactive mechanics (e.g., task completion, environmental feedback, social interactions) as well as personal memories and reflective engagement (Bopp et al., 2016). For individuals experiencing stress or isolation, games may function as emotional sanctuaries. Positive emotions can increase playtime and frequency (Bringula, Lugtu, Uy, & Aviles, 2020), suggesting that authentic feelings toward the game may exert a moderating effect on cognitive absorption. Many games are intentionally designed to elicit dopamine release (Pacewicz, 2015) and regulate adrenaline (Perich Pallaruelo, 2020) via reward mechanisms, progression systems, and social validation. Such emotional reinforcement may deepen immersion while simultaneously reducing motivation for real-world engagement, amplifying in-game cognitive absorption, and diminishing external interaction. Based on this theoretical and empirical foundation, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H2: Players who play ACNH more frequently will report higher levels of real-world disconnection during ACNH gaming.

H3: The association between the frequency of playing games and real-world disconnection is moderated by the perceived rich experience during ACNH gaming.

H4: The association between the frequency of playing games and real-world disconnection is moderated by the perceived aesthetics during ACNH gaming.

H5: The association between the frequency of playing games and real-world disconnection is moderated by perceived imaginativeness during ACNH gaming.

2.2. Model Construction

2.2.1. Dataset

The study utilized an observational, cross-sectional dataset comprising 640 Animal Crossing: New Horizons (ACNH) players from 29 countries. The dataset, peer-reviewed and openly published in *Data Intelligence* (Vuong et al., 2021), was collected between 15 and 30 May 2020 via an online survey administered through Google Forms. This platform was selected due to its accessibility, confidentiality safeguards, and seamless distribution through shareable links. Before survey dissemination, community moderators or administrators on Discord, Reddit, and Facebook were contacted for approval. The study's objectives, procedures, and compliance with community guidelines were fully described, and the survey post—containing a detailed study explanation and the questionnaire link—was shared only after receiving explicit permission. Informed consent was required before participation. As an incentive, the first 100 respondents received a US\$5 Amazon gift card, followed by US\$2 cards for the next 200 participants.

A pilot survey involving 15 students from Japan, Singapore, the United States, and Vietnam was conducted to ensure clarity and reliability. Their feedback informed minor adjustments to enhance measurement accuracy. To minimize missing data, all questions were set as mandatory. Contact details of the research team were provided for real-time assistance, and all inquiries were responded to promptly. Upon completion of data collection, a formal closure announcement was circulated across all participating communities. The responses were exported in both Excel (.xls) and CSV formats. Data cleaning consisted of clarifying ambiguous responses, coding variables, and conducting validation checks through visual inspection and descriptive statistical analysis.

Ethical review and approval were waived by Phenikaa University, as the research involved non-interventional social inquiry without deception or collection of sensitive personal information. The study followed the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki, ensuring voluntary and anonymous participation, and full adherence to social science ethical standards. Participants were informed of the study's purpose and procedures and were advised of their right to withdraw at any time without consequence. No personally identifiable information was collected, and all data were handled confidentially and exclusively for academic purposes.

Among the 640 participants, 64.38% ($n = 412$) identified as female. The largest share of respondents came from North America (55%), followed by Asia (28.13%) and the European Union (14.38%), with the remaining 2.5% from other regions. The ethnic distribution reflected this geographical pattern, with White (54.22%) and Asian (31.25%) participants comprising the majority. Over half were undergraduate students (52.5%), and most were single and never married (61.09%). The sample predominantly consisted of young adults aged 18–30 (72.8%), with overall ages ranging from 11 to 55. Additionally, 63% ($n = 403$) reported stable employment, while 13.44% indicated that they did not own a pet or a garden.

2.2.2. Variable Selection and Rationale

In this study, six key variables were selected to examine how the duration of self-isolation/social distancing, game-play experience, and gameplay frequency jointly influence the feeling of disconnection from the real world during gameplay. The outcome variable, *LostConnection*, captures the extent to which respondents experienced real-world detachment while playing ACNH. It was measured using a five-point Likert scale (ranging from ‘not at all’ to ‘extremely’) based on the statement: “I lost connection with the outside world while playing the game.”

The predictor variables include *ACNHFrequency*, *RichExperience*, *AestheticPleasing*, *Imaginative*, and *SelfIsolation*. *ACNHFrequency* reflects gameplay frequency, while *RichExperience*, *AestheticPleasing*, and *Imaginative* assess sensory and imaginative immersion. These three variables were extracted from the Sensory and Imaginative Immersion subscale of the Game Experience Questionnaire (GEQ). Although the original subscale contains six items, only these three were selected to capture distinct dimensions of immersion while excluding items that were either not applicable to ACNH (e.g., narrative-related elements) or appeared conceptually redundant. Descriptions of all variables are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Variable Description

Variable (Variable in the original dataset)	Description	Data Type	Values
<i>SelfIsolation</i> (B2)	The respondent’s length of being self-isolated/social distancing	Categorical	1 = No self-isolation/social distancing 2 = Less than a week 3 = More than a week 4 = More than two weeks 5 = More than three weeks 6 = More than a month
<i>ACNHFrequency</i> (D5)	The ACNH game-playing frequency of the respondent	Numerical	1 = Almost every week 2 = Every week 3 = Almost every day 4 = Everyday
<i>RichExperience</i>	Game-playing feeling	Numerical	1 = not at all

(F30)	of rich experience		2 = slightly 3 = moderately 4 = fairly 5 = extremely
<i>AestheticPleasing</i> (F12)	Game-playing feeling of aesthetically pleasing	Numerical	
<i>Imaginative</i> (F18)	Game-playing feeling of imagination	Numerical	
<i>LostConnection</i> (F31)	Game-playing feeling of real-world detachment	Numerical	

2.2.3. Analytical Model

To examine the Hypotheses, three different models were constructed, ranging from simple to complex models. The first model is as follows:

$$LostConnection \sim Normal(\mu, \sigma) \quad (1.1)$$

$$\mu_i = \alpha_{SelfIsolation[i]} + \beta_1 * ACNHFrequency_i \quad (1.2)$$

$$\alpha \sim normal(M_\alpha, S_\alpha) \quad (1.3)$$

$$\beta \sim normal(M_\beta, S_\beta) \quad (1.4)$$

The probability distribution around the mean μ_i follows a normal distribution, where the spread of the distribution is determined by the standard deviation σ . Here, μ_i represents the level of disconnection from the real world while playing the game of player i . $\alpha_{SelfIsolation[i]}$ specifies six intercepts, corresponding to six length levels of self-isolation/social distancing during COVID-19 among game players.

The second and third models were constructed to examine the non-additive effects of interactions between immersion and game-playing frequency on the level of lost connection to real life. While the second model only includes the interaction terms, the third model also includes the parameters of different aspects of immersion separately.

$$LostConnection \sim Normal(\mu, \sigma) \quad (2.1)$$

$$\mu_i = \alpha_{SelfIsolation[i]} + \beta_1 * Selfisolation_i + \beta_2 * ACNHFrequency_i + \beta_3 * ACNHFrequency_i * RichExperience_i + \beta_4 * ACNHFrequency_i * AestheticPleasing_i + \beta_5 * ACNHFrequency_i * Imaginative_i \quad (2.2)$$

$$\alpha \sim normal(M_\alpha, S_\alpha) \quad (2.3)$$

$$\beta \sim normal(M_\beta, S_\beta) \quad (2.4)$$

The structure of Model 3 is as follows:

$$LostConnection \sim Normal(\mu, \sigma) \quad (3.1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_i = & \alpha_{SelfIsolation[i]} + \beta_1 * Selfisolation_i + \beta_2 * ACNHFrequency_i + \beta_3 * \\ & ACNHFrequency_i * RichExperience_i + \beta_4 * ACNHFrequency_i * \\ & AestheticPleasing_i + \beta_5 * ACNHFrequency_i * Imaginative_i + \beta_6 * RichExperience_i \\ & + \beta_7 * AestheticPleasing_i + \beta_8 * Imaginative_i \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\alpha \sim normal(M_\alpha, S_\alpha) \quad (3.3)$$

$$\beta \sim normal(M_\beta, S_\beta) \quad (3.4)$$

Model 1a has two coefficients (β_1 - β_2), Model 2 has five coefficients (β_1 - β_5), and Model 3 has eight coefficients (β_1 - β_8). The intervals are distributed as a normal distribution around the mean M_α with the standard deviation S_α , while the coefficients of the predictor variables are distributed as a normal distribution around the Mean, denoted M_β , and with the standard deviation, denoted S_β .

Then, we employ the Akaike weight comparison to determine the most suitable model for interpretation. Akaike weights convert statistics of Pseudo-BMA without Bayesian bootstrap, Pseudo-BMA with Bayesian bootstrap, and Bayesian stacking into a total weight of 1, which is partitioned among the considered models, making it easier to compare their relative predictive accuracy. As can be seen from Table 2, Model 2 has the highest weight in all categories, so it is the model with the highest prediction accuracy on the data. Thus, it will be used for result interpretation. The logical network of Model 2 is shown in Figure 1.

Table 2: Model weight comparison

Model	Pseudo-BMA without Bayesian bootstrap	Pseudo-BMA with Bayesian bootstrap	Bayesian stacking
Model 1	0.000	0.000	0.035
Model 2	0.586	0.550	0.617
Model 3	0.414	0.450	0.348
Fittest model	Model 2	Model 2	Model 2

Figure 1. Logical network of Model 2

2.3. Analysis and validation

The present study employed the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) analytics for both methodological and theoretical reasons. First, BMF integrates the cognitive reasoning strength of Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITT) with the inferential capabilities of Bayesian statistics, making it highly suitable for analyzing complex, uncertain, and information-intensive psychological (Nguyen, La, Le, & Vuong, 2022; Vuong, Nguyen, & La, 2022). Second, Bayesian inference treats both known and unknown parameters as probabilistic variables (Csilléry, Blum, Gaggiotti, & François, 2010; Gill, 2014), allowing for flexible and parsimonious model specification. Through Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling, it also facilitates efficient estimation of sophisticated models, including multilevel and nonlinear structures (Dunson, 2001). Third, compared with frequentist techniques, Bayesian analysis provides interpretive advantages—most notably the use of credible intervals, which enable continuous probabilistic evaluation of uncertainty rather than relying on binary significance tests based on p-values (Halsey, Curran-Everett, Vowler, & Drummond, 2015; Wagenmakers et al., 2018).

The current study employed Bayesian multilevel modeling, so it also provides several advantages. First, this approach enables the structured integration of background knowledge to generate more realistic inferences about the phenomena under investigation. When applied through multilevel or hierarchical modeling, this capability is expanded further by allowing simultaneous analysis of interrelated quantities across

different levels (Spiegelhalter, 2019). Second, multilevel modeling helps avoid overfitting in small-sample groups and mitigates noise by shrinking extreme estimates toward the overall mean. Third, Bayesian hierarchical models can efficiently propagate uncertainty across model levels, resulting in more realistic posterior estimates and credible intervals, which also support the interpretation of a non-linear relationship (McElreath, 2018).

Priors play a central role in Bayesian modeling. Given the exploratory nature of this study, uninformative (flat) priors were applied to limit their influence on parameter estimation (Diaconis & Ylvisaker, 1985). To test the robustness of the posterior estimates, a prior-sensitivity analysis was conducted by re-estimating the model using a skeptical prior distribution [Normal(0, 0.5)], reflecting conservative expectations regarding the associations. Consistency of posterior estimates across both prior settings indicates stability and limited dependence on prior assumptions. Further, the use of priors helps alleviate multicollinearity. As Leamer (1973) explained, multicollinearity in Bayesian modeling reflects a “weak data problem,” where inflated standard errors and overlap between prior and posterior distributions in certain parameter subspaces hinder inference. Empirical studies demonstrate that Bayesian models with informative priors can outperform Ridge regression in mitigating multicollinearity issues (Adepoju & Ojo, 2018; Jaya, Tantular, & Andriyana, 2019).

Following the model fitting process, we employed Pareto-smoothed importance sampling leave-one-out (PSIS-LOO) diagnostics to assess the goodness-of-fit of the model (Vehtari & Gabry, 2019; Vehtari, Gelman, & Gabry, 2017). The LOO formula is as follows:

$$LOO = -2LPPD_{loo} = -2 \sum_{i=1}^n \log \int p(y_i | \theta) p_{post(-i)}(\theta) d\theta$$

The posterior distribution $p_{post(-i)}(\theta)$ denotes the posterior distribution computed after excluding the observation i . In the PSIS method, k -Pareto values are used to identify influential observations. Values below 0.5 indicate that the model fits well, while values above 0.7 suggest the presence of influential data points affecting the LOO estimate.

For models demonstrating a good fit with the data, we proceeded with convergence diagnostics and result interpretation. We used both statistical measures and visual illustrations to validate convergence. Statistically, the effective sample size (n_{eff}) and the Gelman–Rubin shrink factor ($Rhat$) were employed. The n_{eff} value larger than 1000 indicates a sufficient number of effective samples for reliable inference (McElreath, 2018). The $Rhat$ value should be close to 1 for convergence, with values exceeding 1.1 indicating non-convergence (Brooks & Gelman, 1998). Visually, the Markov chains’ convergence was also validated using trace plots. In this study, both models were constructed under four Markov chains. Thus, we need to evaluate the convergence between Markov chains before further results interpretation.

The Bayesian analysis was conducted in the R platform using the open-access **bayesvl** package v1.0.0, which offers robust visualization capabilities (La & Vuong, 2019; Vuong & La, 2025). To ensure data transparency and facilitate reproducibility, all data and code snippets from this study have been deposited on an online server for public access and reuse. The dataset and code can be accessed at: <https://zenodo.org/records/17695008>.

3. Results

The PSIS-LOO diagnostics showed that all k -values were below the recommended threshold of 0.5, indicating that the constructed model demonstrated a good fit to the data (Figure 2). This provides confidence that the estimated parameters can be interpreted with reliability.

Figure 2. Model 2's PSIS-LOO diagnosis of MCMC simulations, estimated using uninformative priors.

Figure 3 displays the trace plots, which demonstrate excellent mixing and stationarity across all parameters, with chains exploring the same parameter regions and showing no evidence of divergence or poor convergence.

Figure 3. Model 2's trace plots from MCMC simulations, estimated using uninformative priors.

Table 3 presents the posterior distribution statistics for Model 2's parameters. The model includes mean estimates (*Mean*), standard deviations (*SD*), *Rhat* values, and effective sample sizes (*n_eff*). All parameters demonstrate excellent convergence properties with *Rhat* values of 1.00 and substantial effective sample sizes (>7,000), confirming reliable posterior estimation.

Table 3. Model 2's estimated posterior distribution

Parameters	Uninformative priors				Informative priors			
	Mean	SD	<i>n_eff</i>	<i>Rhat</i>	Mean	SD	<i>n_eff</i>	<i>Rhat</i>
<i>ACNHFrequency</i>	-0.37	0.12	7031	1.00	-0.35	0.12	8271	1.00
<i>ACNHFrequency*AestheticPleasing</i>	0.01	0.02	7314	1.00	0.01	0.02	8215	1.00
<i>ACNHFrequency*RichExperience</i>	0.12	0.02	8484	1.00	0.12	0.02	9584	1.00
<i>ACNHFrequency*Imaginative</i>	0.00	0.02	9476	1.00	0.00	0.02	9663	1.00
<i>a_Selfisolation[No isolation]</i>	2.23	0.23	10269	1.00	2.20	0.22	12763	1.00

<i>a_SelfIsolation[Less than a week]</i>	3.00	0.30	13275	1.00	2.99	0.30	14215	1.00
<i>a_SelfIsolation[More than a week]</i>	3.25	0.31	11529	1.00	3.23	0.31	12595	1.00
<i>a_SelfIsolation[More than two weeks]</i>	3.02	0.26	12999	1.00	2.99	0.26	13584	1.00
<i>a_SelfIsolation[More than three weeks]</i>	3.11	0.26	12017	1.00	3.09	0.26	13423	1.00
<i>a_SelfIsolation[More than a month]</i>	2.46	0.22	11812	1.00	2.44	0.22	13144	1.00
<i>a0_SelfIsolation</i>	2.84	0.35	1876	1.00	2.82	0.34	3199	1.00
<i>sigma_SelfIsolation</i>	0.61	0.33	3018	1.00	0.61	0.32	4403	1.00

Figure 4 presents the posterior distributions of the intercepts, illustrating an inverse U-shaped relationship between the duration of self-isolation/social distancing and the level of real-world disconnection during gameplay. Specifically, disconnection tends to increase as self-isolation/social distancing lengthens; however, for individuals experiencing isolation beyond approximately two weeks, the level of disconnection begins to decline.

Figure 4: Estimated posterior distributions of the intercepts

The estimated results using uninformative priors reveal that *ACNHFrequency* is negatively associated with *LostConnection* ($M_{ACNHFrequency} = -0.37$ and $S_{ACNHFrequency} = 0.12$), and this association is positively moderated by *RichExperience* ($M_{ACNHFrequency*RichExperience} = 0.12$ and $S_{ACNHFrequency*RichExperience} = 0.02$). These results indicate a complex interaction between gameplay frequency and perceived rich experience in shaping the degree of real-world disconnection. Meanwhile, the moderation effects of *AestheticPleasing* and *Imaginative* are unambiguous. Figure 5, which presents the 95% Highest Posterior Density Intervals (HPDIs) of the coefficients, demonstrates that the effects of *ACNHFrequency* and *ACNHFrequency*RichExperience* are highly reliable. Moreover, the results estimated using informative priors are consistent with those obtained from uninformative priors, indicating that the findings are robust to prior specification.

Figure 5. Estimated coefficients' posterior distributions obtained from MCMC simulations, using uninformative priors

To facilitate the interpretation of the complex non-linear interplay between game-playing frequency, perceived richness of game experience, and disconnection level, the mean coefficient values reported in Table 3 were applied to generate the interaction plot in Figure 6. The figure illustrates that a perceived rich experience is consistently and

positively associated with greater disconnection from the real world. In contrast, the association between game-playing frequency and disconnection varies depending on the immersiveness level. Specifically, when immersiveness is high (i.e., fairly or extremely immersed), higher game-playing frequency corresponds to a higher level of disconnection. Conversely, when immersiveness is low (i.e., slightly or not at all immersed), higher game-playing frequency appears to be associated with reduced disconnection.

Notably, players who report both high immersiveness and high game-playing frequency constitute the group with the highest observed disconnection level. In contrast, those who exhibit low immersiveness but high game-playing frequency demonstrate the lowest level of disconnection. This finding highlights the crucial moderating role of immersiveness in shaping how gameplay engagement influences psychological detachment from real-world contexts.

Figure 6. Interaction between rich experience and gameplaying frequency in determining real-world disconnection

4. Discussion

This study clarifies critical insights into the interplay between the frequency and quality of gaming experiences and duration of social isolation, ultimately affecting an individual's perceptions of disconnection from the external world. The BMF analytics result in several major findings.

First, we found a non-linear, inverse U-curve relationship between the duration of self-isolation/social distancing and the perception of disconnection. Specifically, the self-isolation/social distancing is initially positively associated with the perception of disconnection, but this pattern may plateau or even diminish over time. The U-curve relationship may be explained by game players' psychological adaptation mechanisms. Such dynamics are consistent with earlier research on coping strategies employed during prolonged crises, which suggests that individuals gradually recalibrate their expectations and cultivate resilience over time (Mirhadi, Iacovides, & Denisova, 2024). In other words, the longer individuals undergo self-isolation or social distancing, the greater their likelihood of adapting to a new lifestyle that redefines their interactional boundaries. Over time, players may learn to differentiate between engagement with virtual environments and interactions with the altered external reality—one characterized by physical confinement, disruption of previous routines, and progressive adoption of new behavioral patterns. This cognitive shift can enhance their capacity to regulate immersion and reinterpret virtual experiences relative to real-world constraints. Such adaptations may influence not only how players perceive the gaming environment but also how they process sensory and informational stimuli during gameplay. Therefore, future research should explore how the transformation of environmental conditions—particularly prolonged confinement, lifestyle reconfiguration, and reduced physical interaction—modulates the psychological effects of gaming. Investigating these dynamics would provide meaningful insights into the role of virtual engagement in psychological resilience or vulnerability during periods of social and ecological stress.

Second, the study demonstrates that immersiveness—proxied by the perceived richness of game experience—plays a significant moderating role in shaping the relationship between game-playing frequency and psychological detachment from real-world contexts. Specifically, among players with high immersiveness (i.e., fairly or extremely immersed), increased game-playing frequency predicts greater disconnection. Conversely, for players with low immersiveness (i.e., slightly or not at all immersed), higher game-playing frequency is associated with reduced disconnection.

From the GITT perspective, frequent interaction with the game enables the mind to absorb, process, evaluate, and compare information more efficiently, gradually reducing informational entropy accumulated at the onset of gameplay. Immersiveness reflects the mind's filtering process, which either reinforces or dampens information absorption. When immersiveness is high, the mind is more inclined to prioritize game-related information, thereby amplifying the absorption of ACNH's virtual environmental cues as gameplay frequency increases. In contrast, when immersiveness is low, the cognitive filter tends to deprioritize such information, making it less likely to be retained or utilized in relative to real-world information. Furthermore, frequent gameplay among low-immersiveness players may provide opportunities to contrast in-game and real-world circumstances, helping them recognize the distinction between virtual and actual environments. This recognition reduces cognitive entropy and consequently lowers

psychological detachment. This reasoning approach can help explain the observed pattern whereby players with both high immersiveness and high gameplay frequency report the highest disconnection levels, while those with high gameplay frequency but low immersiveness exhibit the lowest levels of disconnection.

Second, the study reveals that the level of immersiveness (proxied by the perceived rich experience) significantly moderates the relationship between game-playing frequency and psychological detachment from real-world contexts. Specifically, among players with high immersiveness (i.e., those who feel fairly or extremely immersed), increased game-playing frequency predicts greater disconnection. In contrast, for players with low immersiveness (i.e., those who feel slightly or not at all immersed), higher game-playing frequency is associated with reduced disconnection. From the GITT perspective, the frequency of interacting with the game allows the mind to absorb, process, evaluate, compare, and come to recognize the game information better, which helps reduce the enhanced entropy while starting to play the game. The immersiveness can proxy the mind's filtering process that either reinforces the information or dampens the absorption. When the immersiveness is high, the more likely the mind will prioritize information of the game's world and mechanism, which amplifies the absorption of ACNH information as players play more frequently. In contrast, when the immersiveness is low, the filter tends to deprioritize information absorbed from the game, making it less likely to be stored and utilized in relative to the information of the new reality. Moreover, among those players, more frequent game playing provides them with the conditions to evaluate and compare the in-game and real-world information, which allows them to recognize the differences between virtual and real worlds, reduce the mind's entropy, and lower their psychological detachment. This reasoning helps explain why players who report both high immersiveness and high game-playing frequency constitute the group with the highest observed disconnection level, whereas those who exhibit low immersiveness but high game-playing frequency demonstrate the lowest level of disconnection.

However, only the perceived rich experience demonstrates a clear moderating effect, whereas the effects of imaginativeness and aesthetics remain ambiguous. This discrepancy can be attributed to the conceptual differences between these constructs. Perceived rich experience reflects how informationally dense the gameplay is perceived to be, encompassing sensory engagement, perceived meaningfulness, and the complexity of interaction with the game's ecosystems. Such richness enables the mind to absorb and process granular feedback from gameplay (e.g., socio-ecological consequences, behavioral outcomes), thereby exerting a direct influence on system-level cognitive processing related to immersion and psychological detachment. In contrast, aesthetic pleasure primarily enhances sensory enjoyment without necessitating deeper cognitive integration or evaluative feedback processing. As a result, it is less likely to substantively affect how information from the virtual and real worlds is interpreted. Similarly, imaginativeness supports abstraction and creative engagement, but this mechanism is highly dependent on individual cognitive capabilities and types. Rather

than anchoring cognition within the game's informational system, it may redirect attention toward self-generated or fantasy-driven narratives, which could either amplify or reduce detachment depending on the player's mindset.

These results align with previous research indicating that deeper emotional engagement, rather than superficial aesthetic appreciation, can play a more critical role in shaping the social and psychological ramifications of digital media (Cheng, 2025). Future studies should further investigate the cognitive mechanisms underlying the moderating role of perceived rich experience by incorporating longitudinal or experimental designs to capture how players process and retain informational feedback from gameplay over time. Additionally, research employing qualitative or neurocognitive methods could help clarify whether and how imaginative and aesthetic engagement differentially influence information filtering and psychological detachment across diverse player profiles.

Practically, these findings highlight the need to design digital environments that foster immersive engagement while incorporating psychological safeguards. Game developers, mental health professionals, and policymakers should consider not only the frequency of digital engagement but also the emotional and cognitive structure of virtual experiences. Encouraging mindful and intentional gameplay—particularly during periods of social or ecological crisis—may mitigate risks of psychological detachment while enhancing the therapeutic value of digital platforms. Future research should investigate longitudinal patterns of gaming behavior and emotional adaptation, as well as examine cross-cultural differences in how players interpret and internalize virtual experiences. Extending the scope beyond ACNH to include a broader range of game genres and platforms would deepen our understanding of the digital mindscape and its implications for psychological well-being and social connectedness.

Several limitations of the study merit consideration. First, the dataset is derived from a cross-sectional design, which restricts causal interpretation as it does not account for temporal dynamics in variable changes over time. Second, reliance on self-reported data may introduce response bias. Third, although the sample spans 29 countries, the findings may not fully generalize across geographic regions, as cultural interpretations of self-isolation, gaming experiences, emotional expression, and real-world disconnection likely vary across socio-cultural contexts. Finally, the study focuses exclusively on *Animal Crossing: New Horizons*, which features distinct mechanics and aesthetic attributes. As such, the results may not be directly applicable to other virtual environments with different structural or experiential characteristics.

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